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ON BUSINESS ETHICS: VALUES HIERARCHY AND THE ROLE OF RESEARCH

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Abstract:

The traditional mistrust towards business managers is based on different scandals such as *Enron* or *Worldcom*. However, since the 60's, a more social view of business starts to prevail. In this regard, business ethics play a paramount role in trying to conduct business activities ethically. But, the practice of ethics is not easy. Further researches are needed to attempt to approach the truth. This paper aims to contribute to the development of business ethics by looking into different aspects on ethics application such as values hierarchy and ethical actions assessment. We explain that managers would appreciate a ranking of ethical values and actions in order to behave ethically, and especially in a financial crisis context. Then we look into the feasibility to obtain this ranking, and question how empirical research could help.

Keywords: *business ethics; values; ethics research*

SOBRE LA ÉTICA EN LOS NEGOCIOS: JERARQUÍA DE VALORES Y EL PAPEL DE LA INVESTIGACIÓN

Resumen:

La tradicional desconfianza hacia los gestores empresariales se fundamenta en diferentes escándalos como los de *Enron* o *Worldcom*. Con todo, desde los años 60, comienza a prevalecer una visión más social de los negocios. En este sentido, la ética empresarial desempeña un papel crucial al tratar de que las actividades de los negocios sean éticas. Con todo, practicar la ética no es fácil. Hacen falta más investigaciones para tratar de aproximarse a la verdad. Este artículo pretende contribuir al desarrollo de la ética en los negocios centrándose en diferentes aspectos de la aplicación de la ética, como la jerarquía de valores y la valoración de las acciones éticas. Se explica cómo los gestores apreciarían un ranking de valores y acciones éticas de cara a comportarse éticamente, y especialmente en un contexto de crisis financiera. A partir de ahí se plantea la viabilidad de obtener dicho ranking, y se cuestiona cómo puede contribuir a ello la investigación empírica.

Palabras clave: *ética en los negocios; valores; investigación en ética*

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1. Introduction

According to Llano (1990, p. 3), at present “we are immersed in the human events time, where a conjunction between technology and humanism, between effectiveness and culture, between economic goals achievement and the fulfilment of the most human of humankind is possible. The field where this conjunction is taking place is, precisely, the firm”. On his part, the “guru of the gurus”, Peter Drucker claims that “...management also deals with people, their values, their growth and development –and this makes it a humanity– [, ...it] is deeply involved in spiritual concerns, the man nature, the good and evil” (Drucker 1989). These two quotes illustrate that the fields of ethics and business management are more and more intrinsically related; prestigious experts from both knowledge fields do not differ much in their approaches.

Business and ethics have been studied together for years, especially from the Philosophy and Ethics viewpoints. Since the 60’s the concept of “applied ethics” began to be used in occidental culture countries and different disciplines such as Biotechnologies, Medicine, Economics and Business turned to be the focus of Philosophy studies. Until that time the foundation of moral had been the mainstream.

Applied ethics arose due to an imperative from social reality which needed multidisciplinary answers in morally pluralist societies (Cortina 2005). It was time to apply all the developments on moral and ethics foundation in order to try to make a better world for humankind. However, the practice of ethics is not as simple as it seems in theory. Further contributions are always welcome when attempting to approach the truth. This paper aims to contribute to the development of applied ethics, especially, business ethics, by looking into different aspects regarding ethics application such as values and ethical actions hierarchy, ethical behaviour assessment and how the present financial crisis hinders firms’ ethical reputation. We explain that managers would appreciate a ranking of ethical values and actions in order to behave ethically. Then we look into the feasibility to obtain this ranking, and question how empirical research could help.

2. Values and ethical behaviour

Unfortunately, it is not unusual to learn about some scandals in the business world whose origins can be found in corrupt behaviours of managers of public or private organizations. These types of behaviour are based on an evident lack of ethical values in the managing style of these companies. Ethical behaviour is always related to values which constitute a basic concept to start to approach ethics.

The term “value” has different meanings. In Philosophy it represents the quality different realities have, which are considered goods and, therefore, desirables. This is a broad and complex perspective which is out of the scope of this work. Here values are defined as the principles that rule the behaviour of whether a person, group of people or an organization. However, we must keep in mind that in the end, final active subjects of ethical behaviour are always people.

Another previous concept is to determine what we understand by “ethical behaviour”. If we follow a Thomistic perspective, ethical behaviour would imply an action in accordance to human nature that fulfils God’s antecedent will. For an agnostic, however, it would embrace an action in accordance with human nature, that is, according to an Aristotelian naturalist conception. In both cases we see we come to the same conclusion. But still we could not provide a list naming different ethical actions. In this sense, it is very useful for the study of ethics the Universal Declaration of Human Rights¹. Unique starting point as for “values” generally and absolutely accepted.

Obviously, we all agree that honesty, justice or integrity are desirable values in any human action. The difficulty arises when determining which specific actions comprise these values and how to determine them. For example, an upright person is that who act according to his or her convictions, but one can be upright and at the same time unfair if these convictions are wrong. That is, there is a necessity to specify in a clear and practical way what exactly an ethical behaviour is. This is not a simple task. Some people try to find an answer to this dilemma by arguing that the law can solve this question in each specific case. However, in spite of the fact that the law should fit ethics and justice, it is not always like this. Ethics is wider and more demanding than law since it seeks human fulfilment and law cannot come into this philosophical approach (Díaz-Méndez 2010).

¹ Approved by Resolution 217 A (III) at the United Nations General Assembly held in April 10th, 1948.

3. Some considerations on business ethics

The general public distrust towards business managers motivated by a continuous string of ethics scandals leads people to think that most of them would be willing to undertake unethical acts as long as they get an economic benefit². Cases like *Enron*, *Arthur Andersen* and *Worldcom*, or scandals such as the excessive remuneration in administrator boards and property scandals have contributed to increase this distrust (Díaz-Méndez et al. 2007; Nill and Schibrowsky 2007). There are even some reflections from Nobel prizes like Milton Friedman or John K. Galbraith that reinforce the idea of business as suspicious activities *per se*. Friedman (1970, 1982) held that the only social responsibility of a company is towards its stockholders. Galbraith (1998), on his part, focused on advertising, and considered the creation of new needs for clients the final purpose of this management tool³.

However, since the second half of the 20th century, a more social view of business prevails. Firms are considered beneficial for society because they satisfy clients' needs, and meantime they create jobs and pay taxes. The so-called paradigm of the Triple Bottom Line (3BL) provides an evidence of this shift. The 3BL advocates that an organization's ultimate success should be measured not just by the traditional financial bottom line but also by its social, ethics and environmental performance (Norman and MacDonald 2004: p. 343). The myth of "firm without soul" is being mitigated then. In this context business ethics arises as a consequence of the global concern for *remoralizing* society (Cortina 2005).

Nowadays multiple agents are interested in the application of ethical principles in the market: philosophers, managers, stockholders, international organizations, governments, economists and so on. This implies that there is a consensus about the idea that although a firm final purpose is profit, it can concur with a regulation of the market activity aimed at avoiding non-ethical behaviours.

The current change of direction is feasible because we can assert that ethics is profitable for firms, especially in terms of trust generation (García 2004; Cortina 2005; Guillén 2006). Anyone could find a successful and meantime non-ethical organization. Business ethics cannot be measured in terms of financial profit. As Guillén suggests (2006: p. 16), there are three levels of reasons to justify the application of ethics in business. There is a first group, called reasons of third-order, which deals with those reasons purely of an economic nature, that is, "human quality" can become a source of competitive advantage. This would be the case of a company that donates certain amount of money to a non-profit organization and invests the triple in publicizing it so that this donation is mainly on the benefit of a better reputation. This utilitarian behaviour is not the ideal one, however, it provides evidence of the benefits that the adoption of *theoretically ethical behaviour* (or political ethical behaviour) in the market may give rise.

A second-order group of reasons are of a psychosocial character and are related to the fact that ethical behaviour provides satisfaction to individuals and is requested by society. Internal and external stakeholders of a firm feel more satisfied when feeling they contribute to the welfare of the community. This is why many firms allocate part of their benefits to non-profit organizations (the so-called *cause-marketing*) or other activities of an ethical nature. Finally, a first-order group of reasons apply to individuals' need to behave as human beings. Organizations are made of people and ethics has to do only with humans. Undoubtedly, this later is the superior group of reasons. The best defence of ethics is the personal belief that people must behave ethically, regardless the economic rewards (Llano and Llano 1999). As Saint Thomas Aquinas said, "honour is the reward of virtue". Hence, business ethics are people ethics since ethical behaviour depends only on human behaviour.

4. Approaching an ethical values hierarchy: the role of research

Business ethics is a field of research difficult to study. Scheler (1913) holds the study of values should be based on phenomenological cognition; he rejects the possibility of finding out the philosophy of values from empirical research (Remigiusz 2008). Ethics is a phenomenon that is too qualitative, too subjective and too complex to attempt to model empirically (Tsalikis and Fritzsche 1989). Surveys, for example, would tell us what people (managers, consumers, students, etc.) think about what is good and what is bad,

² Surveys that the Wall Street Journal periodically conduces on business managers point out that most of them would be willing to leave ethics aside in order to succeed.

³ These views belong to the firm conception as "autistic firm" –firms focused on accounting and clients– neglecting moral considerations which supposedly belonged to the private sphere of people (Durán 2005).

but cannot provide us with the truth about what actually is good or bad regardless personal opinions. Indeed, Murphy (2010), in the field of marketing ethics, points out that many researchers are focused in the testing of narrow theoretical propositions. He expresses his concern by saying that "...while it is quite difficult to operationalize generalized theories and models, some marketing scholars have been content to investigate such narrow propositions and theories that the outcome of their work is marginalized. The field of marketing ethics seems increasingly to be using the same narrow lens that has characterized much of the consumer behaviour research over a prolonged period [...] The work of marketing ethics can impact the practice of marketing if researchers keep in mind that they are not engaged in just a narrow academic exercise" (Murphy 2002, p. 171). However, in spite of the fact that empirical research can help little in finding out what ethical values are worthier than others, people –in this case, business people– require some external objective ethical guidance to act according to certain values.

Ethical values are a core issue in the study of ethics. Far from an attempt to define philosophically what a value is, we understand here that values are principles that rule people behaviour. A different question is to approach a classification of values, what embraces even more difficulty. Undoubtedly there must be a values scale; for example, we will agree that health is over beauty, justice is over success, charity is over prestige, or environment preservation is over culture. The same way comes about with business ethics. Values such as wisdom, honesty, humility or justice are some of the most repeated values in business ethics books (Guillén 2006).

The Scheler's (1913) well-known hierarchy of values suggests four categories, ranking them from lowest to highest: (i) *sensory values*: those related to pleasure and pain, the pleasant and the unpleasant; (ii) *vital values*: these deal with health and quality of life differing the noble and vulgar; (iii) *spiritual values*: which go beyond human biological environment, they refer to deep preferences of love and hate; and (iv) *sacred-related values*: these values are experienced as bliss or doubt and indicate how far a person is from holiness, the maximum state of the human being. Thus, the most a person is guided by higher values the more moral that person becomes.

In spite of the fact that this list is quite abstract we can understand what Scheler meant, not all values are alike, their weight will depend on type of people, circumstances, context, time, etc. Business ethics, as an application of ethics, also contemplate a ranking of values. The dilemma comes when trying to provide a similar hierarchy. Business ethics deal with different concerns: environmental issues, health and safety issues, consumer issues (Murphy 2010), labour conditions issues and other issues related to poverty, social inequality, etc. That is to say, the application of the previous values would materialize in different questions for a business man such as *what goes first: my employees' higher quality of life or the environment preservation, consumers' or employees' satisfaction, environment preservation or hunger in the world, closer society problems or developing countries problems, etc.?*

Let us part from the premise that there are ethical and non ethical business people, some cases can be clear to identify but most would be a matter of understanding the deep intentions of actions taken by them. It is not surprising that companies are constantly been observed by different sectors of society who judge every single decision they made. Hence, assessing whether or not the company –better said: that company managers or employees– are ethical or not. This question is especially evident as for Social Corporate Relationships (SCR) decisions.

At present there exists a wide debate on the principles that lead managers to opt for certain SCR actions (Garriga and Melé 2004): the law, political interests, social demands or ethical values. It is true that actions are good or bad according to the honesty of the intentions behind them, but do we really need to aim at finding out these deep intentions? Maybe we aim at finding out that hierarchy of values so as to be able to tell a manager he or she is doing wrong because they are allocating money in a second-category cause while, for example, their employees are not well considered or fairly paid. Perhaps that manager would ask us back, *do you consider the children hunger in Africa is a second-category cause?*

Clearly, we need to be honest with ourselves and try to describe the ideal ethical firm holding a budget constrain. In the literature an ethical firm usually is described as that firm who promotes the fulfilment of its members (Guillén 2006), but actually this theoretical definition does not tell us how to do so. A list of actions ranked according values and circumstances would. We know that values and circumstances do exist however we also see they cannot be transformed in an operative model as research mainstream tends to do with practically every phenomenon.

5. Business ethics in a context of economic crisis

Beyond the aforementioned arguments, the current economic crisis in Europe hinders even more the way managers face business ethical dilemmas. Companies' decisions are being examined very closely by society, media and many researchers. As usual in management research, objective data as investment in different CSR actions, dismissals and contracting figures, salaries reductions, etc. are taken as indicators of ethical business behaviour. With these objective data some quantitative research can be done and some conclusions will come up, but deep intentions can hardly ever be measured in a numerical scale. This does not mean that we are against this type of research on business ethics, we only contend that empirical work cannot determine whether a person is really ethical or not unless we know people inner motivations which usually are complex.

Some actions in firms are clearly unethical; for example, the recent case of the abusive remuneration and retirement pensions of bank administrators in Spain. Other actions can be questionable such as lowering the quality of products; the moral assessment of this measure depends on several factors: what the manager aims to preserve at expense of quality (employees' jobs, environmental or charity-related causes, etc.), what that reduction of quality consists of (is it about packaging, ingredients, service...?), how such change is communicated to the market and, of course what the product is (a car quality is more transcendental than a t-shirt quality). A similar questionable action would be the decision to increase products prices in a dramatic economic crisis. At first sight it sounds even inadmissible, however, we would need to know the foundations of this decision, since only depending on those the action is ethical or not.

6. Final considerations

It is clear from the above discussion that, at least in the theoretical sphere, there is a marked concern nowadays for ethical behaviour at firms. There are two main questions running through this paper: i) what is the foundation of an ethical behaviour?; and ii) how it would be possible to measure and so to be ranked in order of importance?

Ideally through research we could provide a list of ethical actions ranked from lowest to highest so that business men and women could behave according to certain real values hierarchy, thus being moral, and avoiding society and media criticism; however, we cannot help in this. We agree with Scheler (1913) that each particular situation needs deep analysis. For sure, business decisions are good or bad regardless the unexpected consequences they give rise; people's intentions carry the essence of ethics and so the good or evil. There are many reasons of economic nature that lead firms to undertake decisions politically accepted as ethical but real ethics is an inner personal issue.

Finally, we have highlighted that the field of ethics is a clear example where quantitative methods alone can provide only a partial picture. The more complex the reality to study is the more qualitative the methods should be (Gummesson 2008). Dealing with ethics is dealing with complexity and from a management viewpoint further analysis on specific situations are needed to contribute to business ethics theory. We must prevent ethics to be left aside and deem it as a concern only for philosophers; ethics have to do with the *Human* of human beings, just like business ethics. Therefore, we also must prevent it from being considered a quantifiable phenomenon.

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